

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF AIR TRANSPORT MARKET IN
UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS**

Khilola Artikbaeva

Master's Student, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

e-mail: miss.hilola777@gmail.com

Dr. Summera Khalid

Associate Professor, Department of Foreign Economic Activity and Tourism,

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

e-mail: summera.farooque2117@gmail.com

Zulaykho Kadirova

Associate Professor, Head of Department of Foreign Economic Activity and

Tourism, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

e-mail: zulayxo_kadirova@tsuos.uz

Abstract

In 1991, even Soviet Union collapsed, Uzbekistan continued to be in isolation, which results in worsened situations in all the sectors of the country, especially in the industry of tourism as well as the air transport market. In 2017-2018, the number of tourists increased from 2.6 to 5.34 million and this became possible because of new political reforms. However, in other countries except for CIS countries, there was an inadequate amount of air connectivity which keep on reducing traveling desire. A considerable amount of approaches were taken in order to open new opportunities in the development of air transport in Uzbekistan. The research objective is to the development of Uzbekistan as well as to compare this development under reforms taking as an illustration of Uzbekistan for the air transport market. In order to achieve the aim, the study examines the influence of the action between government airports as well as airlines. Furthermore, a certain amount of data was concentrated on Russian and English language sources.

Keywords: Political Reforms, Airlines, Airports, Air Transport Market, Uzbekistan Airways, Tourism

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan, a Central Asian country with diversification in tourist resources, remained an isolated country even after the Soviet Union collapsed in 1991. The first President of Uzbekistan tried to develop and improve the political system as well as the country's economy. However, at the time of his presidency, Uzbekistan was very far from the economy worldwide political network as well as financial integration. For the past 30 years, in the same time neighboring country, Kazakhstan's situation was different (A. Mazhikeyev et al., 2015); (U. Batsaikhan et al., 2017); (M. Kassen, 2018).

The current President of Uzbekistan, in 2016, initiated the effective policy name called "open door". In December 2016, the industry of tourism mark as the status of a strategic sector of the country's economy which lead to the development of the economy and liberalization processes¹.

Table 1: Number of tourist visitors in Uzbekistan

Year	Change Rate	Number of tourist visitors
2014	-5%	1.862.000
2015	3%	1.918.000
2016	6%	2.027.000
2017	33%	2.690.000
2018	99%	5.346.000
2019	26%	6.748.510
2020	-78%	1.504.130
2021	25%	1.881.350

Sources: data.worldbank.org, www.stat.uz

¹ S. Mirziyoyev, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Measures to ensure accelerated Development of Tourism Industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016.

Interpretation: From 2017 to 2018, there was a steep increase in tourist numbers arriving in Uzbekistan (Table 1). Tourists from CIS counted for 93,8% of all travelers to Uzbekistan. The lacking amount of air connectivity was the reason for the small volume of non-CIS tourists. This kind of aggravated development of the air transport market of Uzbekistan was the consequence of the monopolistic position of ‘Uzbekistan Airways (UzA)’ which was the national state-owned carrier. UzA, in the same way as Soviet Aeroflot, kept operating as a huge state organization in the civil air transport industry, that dominated in every related sphere: airport service, air navigation, and certification of personnel for airlines and airports². In order to address these problems, new policy reforms were introduced in the aviation sector, especially passenger air transportation.

The policy reforms included the visa policy, which made it possible for the ever-increasing number of foreign citizens to visit Uzbekistan with a visa exemption (Table 2). Despite the positive effects generated by these policy reforms in Uzbekistan’s air transport market, there is still a need for analytical and more extensive research works. Therefore, this research work shows the consequences of the isolation policy of Uzbekistan as well as its effect on the market air transport. This also compares Uzbekistan’s situation in the aviation industry under the political reforms. Moreover, the researcher provides Uzbekistan’s system of air transport’s conceptual framework from the viewpoint of airports, airlines as well as government (Fig. 1).

Conceptual Framework

² I. Karimov, Presidential Decree on the Creation of the National Air Company of Uzbekistan, 1992. <http://www.lex.uz/docs/148680>

Fig 1. Conceptual framework of tourism strategy

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of the work is based on qualitative data on policy reforms that examine three tourism strategies that are government, airports, and airlines (Fig. 1). But in the case of Uzbekistan state enterprise as well as the government keeping the records under the planned economy in Soviet time. Data is collected from the World Bank Statistics and Tourism and Cultural Heritage Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Many of the researchers give more attention to professional magazine articles on government acts from the sources of the Russian language.

RECENT POLICY REFORMS

Government

Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as soon as he came into power, made many positive changes, the situation of agriculture has been improved, export duties were also reduced, and the influence and the share of the state on small business were weakened. The tourism sector was also modernized. State Committee for Tourism Development was established in order to grow tourism’s contribution to GDP, employment rates, local budget revenues, and quality of people’s living standards, and additionally, the visa regime was also liberalized.

Table 2. Visa exemptions

Countries	Duration	Date
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Armenia	Up to 90 days	August 31, 1991
Azerbaijan		
Belarus		
Georgia		
Kazakhstan		
Moldova		
Russia		
Ukraine		
Poland	Up to 90 days	August 31, 1991 (canceled in 1993)
Kyrgyzstan	Up to 90 days Up to 60 days	August 31, 1991 (canceled in 2000) February 12, 2007 (resumed)
Tajikistan	Up to 90 days Up to 30 days	August 31, 1991 (canceled in 2000) March 16, 2018 (resumed)
Israel	Up to 30 days	February 10, 2018
Indonesia		
Japan		
The Republic of Korea		
Malaysia		
Singapore		
Turkey		
France	Up to 30 days	October 5, 2018
Germany	Up to 30 days	January 15, 2019
Argentina		
Australia		
Brazil		
Canada		

New Zealand		
Switzerland		
Other European Union countries		
UAE	Up to 30 days	March 20, 2019
Visa-free transit (53 countries)	Up to 5 days	July 1, 2018
E-visa (75 countries)	Up to 30 days	-

Source: Uzbek State Committee for Tourism Development

Up to 2018, only 8 countries' citizens could get visa-free access, whereas starting from February 2018 when there was a huge change in visa policy, citizens of many other countries as well were given visa exemptions to enter Uzbekistan. The citizens of Japan, Turkey, Indonesia, Malaysia, Israel, Singapore, and the Republic of Korea were granted access to enter the country and stay without a visa until 30 days. Table 2 provides information about the visa policy and how it was liberalized gradually through the years. The number of tourists increased by nearly 32% just in the year between 2016 and 2017, which shows the justification of the approaches adopted by the current government authorities (Table 1). The recent statistics provide further proof of the effectiveness of the aforementioned decree.

Comparing the conditions of Uzbekistan under the previous and the current presidential administration, the author realized that considering tourism as a driving sector of the economy was actually taken from past experience of the initial years of independence. Nevertheless, the current president's reforms such as strengthening relations with other countries, as well as improving the country's investments (R. Weitz, 2018); (M. Tseretili, 2018); (S. Kudrathodjaev, 2018).

Airline Services

Airline services in Uzbekistan have good prospects as various customers from South East Asia to European countries generate high demand for travel. A320neo and B787-8 were contributing to the success of the nation, whereas the other two central Asian state-owned carriers reorganized the airline. In 2004 and 2005 Kazakhstan and

Kyrgyzstan airlines went bankrupt (N.B. Djoldoshev, 2016). In addition, Tajik Kyrgyzstan Airlines also got into financial losses, and in 2008 and 2009 countries stopped carrying passengers. Thus, Uzbekistan's transformation should be done carefully and gradually.

The reforms in the air transport sector might be divided into two phases. In the first stage, it remained the state organization for civil air transport. The air transport market in Uzbekistan actively started after the administration of the current president who set the task of foreign investment attraction as well as improvement of the transportation for the people in the framework of the state program "Development Strategy for 2017-2021". This way, the national carrier has risen the number of flights for the citizens of the country to foreign destinations such as Russian Federation and cities like Nur-Sultan, Almaty, Seoul, and Istanbul. Moreover, Russian carriers, such as Nordwind Airlines, Red Wings Airlines, and Nordstar, started to fly into Uzbekistan. Additionally, Uza established an online booking system for flight tickets in 2018, providing more convenience for customers to book and pay the airfare online through "Uzcard" bank cards. Later on, in addition to the existing one, "Visa" and "MasterCard" payment methods were also added³. Uza, in the initial stage of reforms between 2017 and 2018, showed an impressive increase in passenger traffic and also in efficiency without its privatization and restructuring (Table 3).

Table 3. The Economic Efficiency rate of Uzbekistan Airways in the period of 2016-2021.

Years	Input			Output	Economic efficiency	
	Routes	Workers	Fleet	passengers		
2016	50	14462	26	2,471,387	0.885	Inefficient
2017	56	14440	26	2,703,412	0.893	Inefficient

³ Press Service of Uzbekistan Airways, Tickets online for international Bank cards, 2017. Available from: <https://www.uzairways.com/en/news/tickets-online-international-bank-cards/Payment> for Uzbekistan Airways' air tickets by MasterCard, 2018. Available from: <https://www.uzairways.com/en/news/payment-uzbekistan-airways-air-tickets-mastercard>

2018	59	14500	27	3,175,320	1	Efficient
2019	58	14500	32	3,300,000	1	Efficient
2020	50	14500	32	900,000	0.316	Inefficient
2021	59	15000	35	3,000,000	1	Efficient

Interpretation: using a Data Envelopment Analysis method (DEA), the input and output data in the period of 2016-2021 was analyzed. The analysis shows the economic efficiency of Uzbekistan Airways. The results show that in 2018 and 2019 the economic efficiency was 1 for both years which shows the efficiency of UzA, whereas the year 2016, 2017, and 2020 shows inefficiency with less than 1. In 2021, however, the company started to operate in an efficient way, which shows a positive recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Airports

Uzbek airports were also influenced positively by the first stage of new policy reforms. In 2018, Terminal 2 of Capital Airport (TAS) has been extended its capacity to 1,200 passengers arriving in an hour. However, TAS has had no chance to grow since then, because of its location in the center of the city similar to the situations that happened to Turkish Istanbul Ataturk Airport (ISL) and Singaporean International Airport Paya Labar (QPG) (E. Dogan et al.,2017); (G. Lohmann et al., 2009). Due to the decisions made wisely and on time, Singapore and Turkey succeeded in enlarging and maintaining traffic flow for the citizens. By the end of the year 2020, relying on the other countries' experiences, the authorities of Uzbekistan also concluded to establish one more new airport on the basis of an airfield name-called "Tashkent-Vostochny". It is functioned to ensure the highest level for the meeting organizations. the function of a new airport is to serve for business transport market as well as civil.

Table 4. UzA Airports and their Passenger Traffic

Airports	2005	2017	2018
Tashkent-TAS	926467	3020178	3572060
Samarkand-SKD	40185	254273	378173

Karshi-KSQ	22661	30540	45414
Termez-TMJ	46134	126734	96988
Andizhan-AZN	20422	74137	62282
Ferghana-FEG	25829	139896	179649
Namangan-NMA	23496	111123	164579
Navoi-NVI	4032	37385	51112
Bukhara-BHK	45415	200421	228704
Urgench-UGC	48042	282135	332171
Nukus-NCU	41673	95649	143363

Source: UzA; Great Circle Mapper

Interpretation: It can be seen from Table 4 that five airports: Karshi, Andizhan, Termez, Navoi, and Nukus showed the smallest numbers of passengers carried in the years between 2005 and 2018. In addition, UzA continues to receive state subsidies. The rational approach to solve these issues would be to dispense with them so as to decrease the costs. Taking into consideration the negative effects of these problems, the next stage of the reforms was to tackle them in a proper way.

The Policy Reforms in the Second Stage

In the second phase of the reforms, a Decree “On Measures for the radical Improvement of Civil Aviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was signed by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev (N.B. Djoldoshev, 2018). It was aimed to de-monopolize civil aviation in Uzbekistan and simultaneously make UzA independent from state subsidies as well as make it a commercial organization. According to the decree, “Uzbekistan Airports” and “Uzbekistan Airways” were established as Joint-Stock Companies (JSC) as well as companies with Limited Liabilities (LLC), “Uzbekistan Airtechnics”, “Training center” and “Uzbekistan Helicopters”, “Training Centre” and “Catering”. “Civil Aviation Agency” and “Uzair navigation” also began operating under the control of the Transport Ministry of Uzbekistan.

Since the decree was adopted, the airports became commercial for the purpose of the state when the state uses them in emergencies. The JSC airports of Uzbekistan are to determine the phase and rates for services provided by the airport and the services

exempted to resident airlines. Nukus, Karshi, and Termez are now using the “fifth air freedom” international airports and Bukhara is using “fifth air freedom” during foreign nationals’ transportation (N.B.Djoldoshev, 2019). In the second phase, policy reforms were more focused on central airports such as Bukhara, Tashkent, and Samarkand, which have more airlines to the east and west. Table 5 shows that Uzbek airports are connecting the eastern and western countries which have long-distance flights.

Table 5. Distances of flight between countries via airports of Uzbekistan

	Amsterdam- Jakarta	Frankfurt- Kuala Lumpur	London- Sydney	London- Perth
Via Tashkent (TAS)	11,385 km	10,056 km	17,077 km	14,690 km
Via Samarkand (SKD)	11,361 km	10,019 km	17,108 km	14,631 km
Via Bukhara (BHK)	11,355 km	10,008 km	17,124	14,603 km
Non-stop	11,353 km	10,001 km	17,016 km	14,499 km

Source: www.gcmap.com

Interpretation: Since Bukhara airport is in the center of the country as well as it is connecting local flights ideally, the table shows that Uzbek airports are capable of linking eastern and western countries due to their convenient geographical position. Bukhara airport is the most ideal one which has a unique position in the airways.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

There are several reasons which prevent entrepreneurs from Uzbekistan and from other countries from establishing a local airline. Firstly, for passenger services and aircraft, there is no competition in ground services. Secondly, there have not been any attempts to make new policies to implement new business models such as low-cost carriers or any others by the government. In addition to that, airport charges and fuel are excessively costly. According to the law, JSC of Uzbekistan Airways should have

prevented from having a monopoly in the country. The government would not stop supporting and granting Uza JSC, even if it did not have the authority over civil aviation. And Uzbekistan Airports JSC can also determine the fees of airport services other than the fees of services for resident airlines such as Uza JSC.

Since the activities of current monopolies are causing harm to small businesses, the government's top priority to develop the country's economy should be to regulate existing monopolies, such as Uza.

- First of all, the Samarkand airport needs reconstruction due to several reasons. One of them is that the Shanghai Cooperation Organization's summit is coming soon, and the second is that by this Tashkent International Airport's workload can be optimized. Nevertheless, the author considers that this is not a rational decision: the distance between the main hub and other transport hubs of the country is around 260 km, which can also be traveled in 2.15 hours by high-speed train.

- Furthermore, the Samarkand airport is located in the center of the region of Samarkand, which is densely populated. There are only 3,105 meters-long runways in the airport. Thus, instead of just reconstructing the current one. there could have been built another gateway in the west of Samarkand, where there is less population and the landscape is also flat.

- If it cannot be Samarkand airport, then Bukhara would be the rational solution to deal with the main hub's workload. Because it is 570 km by land and 439 km by air away from Tashkent and is in the center of Uzbekistan, it is supposed to ideally connect local flights. Moreover, it can be seen from Table 5 that Uza airports, and especially Bukhara, are capable of linking Eastern and Western countries due to their good geographical positions.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan was isolated during the Karimov presidency, so as to prevent the attacks of terrorists in Tashkent, in 1999 and the war between Afghan and the USA. Due to these facts, Uzbekistan carried out political and economic reforms more slowly than other countries of CIS. Uzbekistan's air transport market remained under the conservative planned economy. Between the years of 1992 and 1999, it operated to

fulfill the needs of the people flying in local airlines. Meanwhile, it continued to protect the monopoly of UzA up to 2016. Despite being under isolationism, it can be considered that Uzbekistan's air transport had moderate success as it remained to provide its services while airports in neighboring countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Kazakhstan went bankrupt. While the first president protected the air transport industry from bankruptcy and strengthened the country's air borders, after the new reforms, introduced by the new President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, UzA was de-monopolized and commercialized. In fact, the prior aim of the recent reforms was to make the tourism strategy more oriented toward air transport. These reforms have been implemented in a very rational way so far, and some of them succeeded in fulfilling the main goals.

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